

One Explanation to Rule them All — Ensemble Consistent Explanations

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Abstract

Transparency is a major requirement of modern AI based decision making systems deployed in real world. A popular approach for achieving transparency is by means of explanations. A wide variety of different explanations have been proposed for decision single models. In practice it is not that uncommon to have a set (i.e. ensemble) of models that is used instead of a single model only. Unfortunately, explanation methods for single model are not easily applicable to ensembles – i.e. they would yield an ensemble of explanations which might be less useful and more difficult to understand than a single explanation. We therefore propose a concept for consistently explaining an ensemble of models locally with a single explanation – we propose an abstract concept, as well as a specific implementation using counterfactual explanations.

1 Introduction

Nowadays, transparency is a natural and broadly accepted requirement [parliament and council, 2016] of AI based decision making systems. Usually, transparency is realized by providing explanations of the system’s behavior [Samek *et al.*, 2017; Guidotti *et al.*, 2018]. While it is not yet completely understood what exactly makes up a “good” explanation [Doshi-Velez and Kim, 2017; Offert, 2017], a lot of different explanation methodologies [Molnar, 2019] such as feature relevances/importances [Fisher *et al.*, 2018] and example based methods [Aamodt and Plaza., 1994] like contrasting explanations [Wachter *et al.*, 2017; Verma *et al.*, 2020] have been developed. Furthermore, explanation methods can be classified into global and local methods [Molnar, 2019]: While global methods try to explain the entire system, local methods explain the system for a particular input or small region of input samples only.

To the best of our knowledge, all the existing methods focus on single models only – i.e. they provide explanations of a single model applied to a single input. However, in some scenarios we might have a set/ensemble of systems instead of a single system that must be explained. An ensemble might exist in space – i.e. a set of models

that are applied to some input – or in time – i.e. different snapshots of a single model that is changing over time. An highly relevant application of ensemble models in real world are water distribution networks where different regions of the network are monitored¹ by different systems that are all based on the same available sensors [Perez *et al.*, 2014; Sanz *et al.*, 2016], and thus the entire monitoring system can be interpreted as an ensemble – we will come back to this particular area of application in Section 4.

In this work we propose a concept of explanations for consistently explaining ensembles of models with a single explanation instead of computing an explanation for each model separately which would yield a ensemble of explanations that might be hard to understand. More precisely, our contributions are as follows:

1. We propose the abstract concept of *ensemble consistent explanations* and a particular realization using counterfactual explanations.
2. We empirically demonstrate the usefulness of ensemble consistent counterfactual explanations in sensor fault detection & localization in water distribution networks.

The remainder of this work is structured as follows: First, we briefly review the necessary foundations in Section 2. Next in Section 3, we propose the abstract concept of *ensemble consistent explanations* and subsequently a specific realization using counterfactual explanations which we call *ensemble consistent counterfactual explanations*. Following up on this, we apply and empirically evaluate our proposed ensemble consistent counterfactual explanations on the real-world task of sensor fault identification in water distribution networks in Section 4. Finally, we close our work with a summary and conclusion in Section 5.

2 Foundations

As mentioned in the introduction, there exist a wide variety of different explanation methodologies [Molnar, 2019]. A prominent instance of contrasting explanations are Counterfactual explanations (often just called *counterfactuals*), which state a change to some features of a given input such that the

¹E.g. looking for anomalies such as leakages and sensor faults that might cause water loss or water contamination.

resulting data point, called the counterfactual, causes a different behavior of the system than the original input does. Thus, one can think of a counterfactual explanation as a suggestion of actions that change the model’s behavior/prediction. One reason why counterfactual explanations are so popular is that there exists evidence that explanations used by humans are often contrasting in nature [Byrne, 2019] – i.e. people often ask questions like “*What would have to be different in order to observe a different outcome?*”. For illustrative purposes, consider the example of loan application: *Imagine you applied for a credit at a bank. Unfortunately, the bank rejects your application. Now, you would like to know why. In particular, you would like to know what would have to be different so that your application would have been accepted. A possible explanation might be that you would have been accepted if you had earned 500\$ more per month and if you had not had a second credit card.* Despite their popularity, the missing uniqueness of counterfactuals could pose a problem: Often there exist more than one possible & valid counterfactual – this is called the Rashomon effect [Molnar, 2019] – and in such cases, it is not clear which or how many of them should be presented to the user. One common modeling approach (if this problem is not simply ignored) is to enforce uniqueness by a suitable formalization.

In order to keep the explanation (suggested changes) simple – i.e. easy to understand – an obvious strategy is to look for a small number of changes so that the resulting sample (counterfactual) is similar/close to the original sample, which is aimed to be captured by Definition 1.

Definition 1 ((Closest) Counterfactual Explanation [Wachter *et al.*, 2017]). *Assume a prediction function $h : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ is given. Computing a counterfactual $\vec{x}_{cf} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ for a given input $\vec{x}_{orig} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is phrased as an optimization problem:*

$$\arg \min_{\vec{x}_{cf} \in \mathbb{R}^d} \ell(h(\vec{x}_{cf}), y_{cf}) + C \cdot \theta(\vec{x}_{cf}, \vec{x}_{orig}) \quad (1)$$

where $\ell(\cdot)$ denotes a loss function, y_{cf} the target prediction, $\theta(\cdot)$ a penalty for dissimilarity of \vec{x}_{cf} and \vec{x}_{orig} , and $C > 0$ denotes the regularization strength.

The counterfactuals from Definition 1 are also called *closest counterfactuals* because the optimization problem Eq. (1) tries to find an explanation \vec{x}_{cf} that is as close as possible to the original sample \vec{x}_{orig} [Karimi *et al.*, 2021; Artelt and Hammer, 2019]. However, other aspects like plausibility and actionability are ignored in Definition 1, but are covered in other work [Looveren and Klaise, 2019; Artelt and Hammer, 2020].

3 Ensemble Consistent Explanations

In the following, we assume that we are given a set (i.e. ensemble) of prediction functions $h_i \in \mathcal{H}$, $h_i : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ together with a sample $\vec{x} \in \mathcal{X}$ – we do not care whether this is an ensemble in space or time. We are looking for a single local explanation that consistently explains the behavior of the functions $h_i(\cdot)$ at \vec{x} .

Let $\Gamma(\vec{x})$ be the set of all possible local explanation at $\vec{x} \in \mathcal{X}$ and $\theta : \Gamma \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ be a function that measures the

complexity of a given explanation – i.e. smaller values correspond to a “lower complexity” explanation while the opposite is true for “higher complexity” explanation. Furthermore, let $\Psi : \Gamma \times \mathcal{H} \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function that measures “how well” the explanation explains the behavior of a given function $h_i(\cdot)$ at a given sample – i.e. the function measures the fidelity of the explanation. We assume that $\Psi(\cdot) \geq 0$ holds if the explanation is “correct” and $\Psi(\cdot) < 0$ otherwise. We are looking for a single, low complexity, local explanation $\gamma \in \Gamma(\vec{x})$ that explains the behavior/prediction of all given functions $h_i(\cdot)$ – we formalize this as the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\gamma \in \Gamma(\vec{x})} \theta(\gamma) \\ & \text{s.t. } \Psi(\gamma, h_i, \vec{x}) \geq 0 \quad \forall i \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Since it might be difficult or even impossible to find an explanation that consistently explains all functions $h_i(\cdot)$, we relax the constraint in the original optimization problem Eq. (2) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\gamma \in \Gamma(\vec{x})} \theta(\gamma) + \lambda \sum_i \xi_i \\ & \text{s.t. } \Psi(\gamma, h_i, \vec{x}) \geq 0 - \xi_i \quad \forall i \\ & \quad \xi_i \geq 0 \quad \forall i \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where we introduced variables ξ_i that allow constraint violations – i.e. some functions $h_i(\cdot)$ might not be explained by the explanation γ . However, in order to explain as many functions $h_i(\cdot)$ as possible, such constraint violations are added as a penalty term to the objective, weighted by a penalty $\lambda > 0$.

3.1 Consistent Counterfactual Explanations

In the following, we use counterfactual explanations (see Definition 1 in Section 2) as a specific type of local explanations for realizing the idea of ensemble consistent explanations as described in the previous section.

Note that because we consider a set of prediction functions $h(\cdot)_i$, we might request potentially different target predictions y_{cf_i} in the counterfactual explanation.

Classification

Assuming a set of binary classifier $h_i : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$. We can implement the idea of ensemble consistent explanations by refining Eq. (3) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\vec{x}_{cf} \in \mathbb{R}^d} \theta(\vec{x}_{cf}, \vec{x}) + \lambda \sum_i \xi_i \\ & \text{s.t. } h_i(\vec{x}_{cf}) \cdot y_{cf_i} \geq 0 - \xi_i \quad \forall i \\ & \quad \xi_i \geq 0 \quad \forall i \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Regression

Similar, for a set of regression functions $f_i : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, we refine Eq. (3) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\vec{x}_{cf} \in \mathbb{R}^d} \theta(\vec{x}_{cf}, \vec{x}) + \lambda \sum_i \xi_i \\ & \text{s.t. } d(f_i(\vec{x}_{cf}) - y_{cf_i}) \leq t_i + \xi_i \quad \forall i \\ & \quad \xi_i \geq 0 \quad \forall i \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Figure 1: L-Town network [Vrachimis *et al.*, 2020] – we only use “Area A” where we have 29 pressure and 2 flow sensors.

where $d : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ denotes a function for penalizing prediction errors – e.g. the absolute error or the squared error² – and $t_i \geq 0$ denotes a tolerance threshold on the prediction error of the i -th regression function, since it might be numerically difficult to achieve exactly y_{cf_i} as a prediction.

4 Experiments

We empirically evaluate our proposed *ensemble consistent counterfactual explanations* on sensor fault localization in water distribution networks, which is an important real-world application, – in this context, we use our proposed explanations for identifying a faulty sensor. The implementation of the experiments is publicly available on GitHub³.

4.1 Setup

We use a variation of the popular L-Town water distribution network [Vrachimis *et al.*, 2020] – for the purpose of getting rid of unwanted complex hydraulic dynamics, we remove areas B and C from the original network so that we are left with area A only (see Fig. 1), which consists of 661 nodes and 766 links. We use the 29 optimally placed pressure sensors and the 2 given flow sensors.

We implement a residual based anomaly detection method by means of virtual sensors [El-Zahab and Zayed, 2019; Perez *et al.*, 2014; Sanz *et al.*, 2016; Vaquet *et al.*,]. We build a virtual sensor $f_i : \mathbb{R}^{30} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ for each of the 29 pressure sensors – the virtual sensor tries to predict the pressure at its specific location based on the previous measurements from all other 28 (i.e. $29 - 1$) pressure and 2 flow sensors. The virtual sensors are implemented using linear regression, whereby we use a sliding window of size 3 for averaging the other past sensor values which are then fed into the linear regression. The anomaly detection itself is realized using a simple threshold θ that is estimated during training on a fault free time window – we raise an alarm whenever any predicted pressure $f_i(\vec{x}_{t-1})$ (from the virtual sensor) deviates too much

² $d(a) = a^2$ or $d(a) = |a|$

³ANONYMIZED

Metric	Score (avg. \pm variance)
True Positives	?
True Negatives	?
False Positives	?
False Negatives	?
Detection delay	?

Table 1: Evaluation of anomaly detection

Metric	Score (avg. \pm variance)
Correctly identified	?

Table 2: Evaluation (percentage) of sensor fault localization

from the observed pressure $(\vec{y}_t)_i$:

$$\|f_i(\vec{x}_{t-1}) - (\vec{y}_t)_i\|_\infty > \theta \quad (6)$$

We generate 434 scenarios using the variation of the L-Town network where we place sensor faults of different magnitude – we consider three different magnitudes per fault type – on the pressure sensors. Each scenario is exactly three month long and contains exactly one sensor fault – the first month is always fault free, so it can be used for training the virtual sensors. We consider five different types of sensor faults [Reppa *et al.*, 2016]:

1. A constant is added to the original sensor measurement.
2. Gaussian noise is added to the original sensor measurement.
3. The sensor measurement is set equal to zero.
4. The original sensor measurement is shifted by some amount.
5. An increasingly larger value is added to the original sensor measurement, until a predefined maximum is reached.

4.2 Results

First, we evaluate the performance of the implemented residual based anomaly detection by reporting the mean and variance of the confusion matrix and detection delay (time until the first alarm is raised) over all scenarios – the results are shown in Table 1. We observe that our implemented anomaly detector is consistently able to detect all sensor faults although it has large differences in the detection delay and it might also have troubles precisely pinpointing the time window when the fault is present – although it consistently identifies that there is a fault present (i.e. true positives are equal to one). A more detailed analysis of the results (the raw results are part of the supplement material) reveals that the performance is better for large magnitude faults and worse for small magnitude faults which is not surprising.

Next, we evaluate the fidelity of our proposed *ensemble consistent counterfactual explanations* by trying to identify the faulty sensor from the explanation. For every detected fault (i.e. raised alarm), we compute an ensemble consistent counterfactual explanation by solving Eq. (5) using convex

Figure 2: Illustration of the a virtual pressure sensor: Predicted vs. observed pressure values at node $n549$.

programming – see Fig. 3 for an example of such an explanation –, that is we are looking for a single explanation that tells us how to change the sensor measurements such that no alarm is raised. After an alarm was raised, we aggregate the next five explanations over time by computing a normalized histogram of the proposed changes by the explanations (see Fig. 3) – note that since an anomaly stays active for some time, we have a sequence of permanent alarms. Because the data, the predictions (see Fig. 2) and consequently the explanations are a bit noisy, we select the sensor with the largest magnitude of proposed changes (according to the explanation) as our prediction of the faulty sensor which we then compare with the known ground truth. The results are shown in Table 2. We observe that we are able to correctly identify the faulty sensor in almost every scenario which demonstrates the high fidelity and usefulness of our proposed explanation methodology.

5 Summary & Conclusion

In this work we proposed the concept of *ensemble consistent explanations* for computing explanations of an ensemble of models instead of a single model only. Note that the ensemble property might be in space – i.e. a set of models like we the set of virtual sensors we considered in our experiments – or in time – i.e. different instances of a single model evolving over time. Furthermore, we also proposed a specific implementation of this concept using counterfactual explanations yielding *ensemble consistent counterfactual explanations*. For the purpose of an empirical evaluation, we applied our proposed explanations to the (important real-world) problem of sensor fault detection and localization in water distribution networks. We observed that our proposed explanations show very good performance for explaining the detected anomalies and identifying the faulty sensors.

Although we introduced a novel and promising concept of explaining ensemble models which showed great potential in real world applications, we note a couple of limitations and

Figure 3: Illustration of a normalized histogram of aggregated *ensemble consistent counterfactual explanations* in case of a sensor fault at node $n332$.

potential directions for further investigations that can be addressed in future research:

- Although our proposed explanations perform well on identifying the single faulty sensor, it is not clear how well they would perform in case of multiple faulty sensors – or in case of other anomalies such as leakages.
- In this work, we were primarily concerned with an ensemble in space - i.e. a set of models that are applied to the input at the same time. As mentioned in the beginning, another potential use case might be to consider ensembles over time – e.g. considering a model that is changing over time and we are looking for an explanation that is consistent over time.
- We mainly focused on proposing the general idea of ensemble consistent explanations and proposed a specific realization using counterfactual explanations. It remains to study the formal properties (such as robustness) of our proposed ensemble consistent (counterfactual) explanations.
- In this work, we used counterfactual explanations as a specific type of explanations for realizing the abstract concept of our proposed ensemble consistent explanations. However, there also exist other types of explanations that could be used to implement ensemble consistent explanations.

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